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Investigating and Presenting a Favorable Solution for Tourism Development in Balkh Province

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Abstract

Today, tourism activity has a major share in the economic income of countries and many businesses are involved in it, and in many countries, economic development is in the group of investment in tourism activity. One of the most important factors that has caused tourism to grow so much in the world there has been innovation in the provision of services and products, and in many tourism destinations today we see a demand for creative tourism products, and in addition to providing the best services for tourists. The purpose of this research is to study and identify the challenges and opportunities in tourism development in Balkh province. In this study, after studying the research literature using SWOT analysis, identify the challenges and opportunities in tourism development in Balkh province and Based on that, strategies were developed and ranked. Finally, the defense strategy was presented as the most effective strategy on tourism development in Balkh province.

Key words: Afghanistan, Balkh, Tourist, Strategy & SWOT.

Introduction

Tourism is one of the most important activities of contemporary man, which making dramatic changes in the appearance of the earth, changes the political, economic, cultural situation and way of life of human beings. Also, this category is one of the most important factors in the direction of cultural exchange and acquaintance with other nations from various natural, cultural dimensions (Mirakzada & et al, 2011, p. 2). Many authors see tourism as a unique economic opportunity. In recent years, tourism has become a rich source of income in world trade and an important element in improving and regulating the trade balance and balance of payments of many countries (Kazimi, 2006, p. 4)

Tourism today has many capabilities and fans as a smokeless industry. The significant growth of tourism in the last fifty years shows the great economic and social importance of this phenomenon. According to the World Tourism Organization, the total number of tourists in the world in 1950 was about 25 million people and in 2020, about 700 million people, which in 2020 will reach about 1 billion and 600 million people. These figures represent a 7% growth over a fifty-year period (1950-2000), plus tourism revenues in 1980 amounted to 105 billion, which reached 476 billion \$ in 2000 and it will reach about one billion and 590 million dollars in 2020 (Kazimi, 2006, p. 5)

Afghanistan with a history of five thousand years and experiencing different civilizations with ancient historical monuments belonging to different historical periods as well as untouched nature, beautiful landscapes and attractions, fascinating, amazing and rich cultural resources of the people is one of the most attractive countries to attract tourists from other countries and has more opportunities for growth and development of the tourism industry. All them means that Afghanistan has good opportunities for the development and growth of the tourism industry, the beautiful nature and the amazing natural landscapes of Afghanistan, such as the soaring and lush valleys of the south and east, the flowery plains and the covered hills From the velvety greenery of the northern provinces in spring, roaring rivers and foamy waterfalls, winding valleys of the central regions, tempting views

of fruit orchards in different regions, etc., are some of its attractions. In the past, thousands of people from different countries of the world were attracted to them (Anabi, 2018, p. 2).

Tourism is now one of the highest paid industries in the world and is expected to become the largest and most economically profitable industry in the world in the coming years. Many countries have been able to take advantage of this industry in their economic growth by planning and developing their tourist attractions. Tourism planning is something that requires the coordination of various groups such as government agencies, economic actors and the public. The development of this industry in many parts of the world which have unique tourist attractions has led to economic growth and development in those areas. In recent years, every country has tried to develop tourism according to its attractions and use its economic benefits. These efforts have led to the emergence of a variety of tourism in recent years, including cultural, social, recreational, winter, summer, rural, educational, commercial, medical, religious, sports, ecotourism, Geo tourism to be created to give benefits to economic growth of many tourist areas. Afghanistan, with its various natural, historical and cultural attractions, has the capacity and ability to develop tourism in various fields (Ahmadi, 2015, p. 3).

In fact, several factors have caused the lack of growth in the tourism industry in Afghanistan, the most important factors are: security and lack of infrastructure required for tourism development has made it difficult for tourists to enter the country and in addition insufficient knowledge of some officials Tourism, lack of tourism specialists, lack of active and specialized publications in this field and lack of production of attractive television programs are the reasons that have hindered the growth of tourism in Afghanistan (Azimi, 2012, p. 5).

Tourism in any country, including Afghanistan, its positive effects are the direct and indirect employment of this industry and its entrepreneurship, so it is said that the arrival of each tourist in the country is equal to creating 9 job opportunities, and therefore countries strive. In addition to entrepreneurship and poverty reduction, tourism has very positive effects in the social and cultural spheres; Tourism is the best way to exchange culture and tradition and the best ambassador of goodwill to introduce the true and historical face of a country, but insecurity is the main obstacle and challenge in Afghanistan (Ava, 2017, p. 4). This article seeks to identify and analyze the most important opportunities and challenges of tourism development and provide desirable strategies for tourism development in Balkh province.

Literature review

Table 1: Some studies conducted on tourism development in some provinces of Afghanistan are as follows.

Researcher	year	Title	methodology	conclusion
Iskandari, Mahmood	2016	Investigating the practical challenges of developing creative tourism in Bamyan	The ANP method was performed using SQAR analysis	The results of the research, the practical challenges of creative tourism in Bamyan, were identified and based on them, Reducing the existing bureaucracy in the system of Bamyan city and Afghanistan in order to develop creative tourism in Bamyan city and strategies were developed and ranked.
Aman, Smiullah	2018	A review of tourism industry development strategies in Afghanistan	Using descriptive-analytical methodology (a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods) and using SWOT and QSPM models.	The results of the above research, in order to strengthen and develop sustainable tourism in Afghanistan, it is necessary to consider a variety of strategies as a strategic set for tourism policy and management and planning. The main strategy showed that people believe in offensive strategy and experts believe in defense strategy. In fact, this difference in the focal strategy for the development of the tourism industry in the country is limited only in the external aspect of the factors influencing the development of tourism. Internally, the views of both groups are close to each other.

Theoretical foundations of research

According to the definition of the World Tourism Organization, tourism or the exact English equivalent of tourism refers to all the activities of individuals who go to places outside their normal environment in order to spend their leisure time, work and other goals for a period of time which is less than a year. In this way, the scope of tourism goes beyond trips that are made solely for the purpose of spending holidays and spending a few days visiting friends and acquaintances and visiting attractive areas. In its broadest sense, tourism, in addition to the group mentioned, includes people who travel in connection with their work and profession, and those who carry out scientific and research activities. In this way, the range of impact on the environment and its impact on the environment becomes much wider. This is the latest definition provided by the World Tourism Organization (Faraji Rad & et al, 2010, p. 62).

Tourism is one of the most important activities of contemporary man, which along with making dramatic changes in the appearance of the earth, changes the political, economic, cultural, character and way of life of human beings. According to the definitions of the World Tourism Organization, the prerequisite for sustainable tourism development is the integration and coordination of economic, environmental, social and cultural goals. This ensures the long-term benefits of the host community, visiting tourists and the protection of natural

resources and cultural heritage. In this sense, tourism planning and management is a cross-sectoral activity that requires a holistic approach and coordination of various related sectors (Mirakzada & et al, 2011, p. 3)

In addition to defining tourism, it is very important to plan for tourism and classify them; because the demands and services required by all types of tourists are not the same; For example, tourists who travel to visit relatives and friends usually do not need a hotel or even a restaurant outside the home, but use other facilities. On the other hand, for tourists traveling for business, facilities such as hotels and accommodation facilities may be very important and they may not be interested in local markets. It is also possible that the rural tourist has no desire for urban services and spends his entire trip in the village. Accordingly, experts and international organizations have provided various categories of tourism according to different criteria (Kazimi, 2011, p. 24).

Depending on the length of the trip, the means of travel and the type of facilities used, the season and how the trip is organized, as well as the various motivations that give rise to a tourist flow, different forms of tourism can be distinguished from each other. But the factors used to classify the different forms of tourism are not the same. Before the First World War, it was not possible to differentiate the form of tourism according to social classes, while today it is necessary to use factors that include time, place, and means of travel, motivation and purpose. indeed, this type of classification will include the most complete type of tourism classification and will subsequently lead to more detailed planning in line with the goals of tourism development (Faraji Rad & et al, 2010, p. 68).

Classification of types of tourism

Effects of tourism: Usually, the effects and consequences of the presence of tourists in three areas of economic, socio-cultural and environmental are evaluated using specific measures. The presence of tourists in a destination will have positive and negative results that planners and policy makers should pay enough attention to the positive results and negative effects of this presence in order to plan tourism and policy making.

Positive effects of tourism: In general, the positive effects of the tourism industry are divided into three categories: economic effects, obtaining foreign currency, job creation, and fair distribution of income, increasing the speed of money circulation, increasing national income and balancing payments, industry development Handicrafts and export products, development of the country.

Cultural and social effects: cultural exchange, development and progress of public culture, familiarity with the manifestations and culture and civilization of different nations, development of cultural and local activities, raising the level of knowledge and public and social information, strengthening national and international unity.

Environmental Impacts: Improving the quality of the environment to attract and satisfy the needs of tourists, construction and development of places that are needed, preservation of historical monuments and cultural heritage (Lotfi, 2009, p. 193).

In examining the negative effects of tourism development on the culture of communities, some authors have pointed to the commodification of the culture of the host community; this means that the residents offer their cultural products as favorite and demand of the tourists. Induction effect is one of these effects and it is a process that residents blindly imitate the guest culture. Another area of social impact that has received more attention in recent years is health (Kazimi, 2007, p.103).

Basically, the negative consequences of tourism for the environment are divided into three main parts:

1. Resource consumption: including natural resources such as water and soil, changes in the ecology of the region and damage to vegetation and animal life.
2. People's attitude towards the environment: which leads to changes in behavioral patterns and social traumas.
3. Pollution: Water pollution, noise pollution and landscape pollution (Lotfi, 2009, p. 196).

Tourist attractions

In order to attract tourists from different countries and regions to different motives, it is necessary to have suitable resources and attractions. Only by investing in the tourism industry and providing a variety of transportation facilities, accommodation and other services, without proper attractions, one cannot hope for the development of this industry; for this reason, tourist attractions and resources are considered as the main pillars of this industry.

Tourist attractions include: natural and cultural attraction

Natural attractions in destinations are often the first thing that attracts the attention of tourists. Sandy beaches, tropical forests, mountain road kilns and mineral springs are some of these attractions.

Cultural attractions include all the external and formal cultural manifestations of each country that can be seen, displayed or presented in some way. These attractions are part of the tourism product, which is divided into soft (spiritual) and hard (material) attractions (Kazimi, 2007, p.84,88).

Afghanistan has many tourist attractions that unfortunately have not received much attention over the last decade. Currently, insecurity, lack of proper housing facilities and transportation routes are the main challenges facing the tourism industry in Afghanistan. Hundreds of thousands of tourists from all over the world are prevented from coming to Afghanistan every year due to lack of security and suitable tourism facilities, thus wasting one of the best opportunities for the development and growth of the country's economy in vain. In order to revive the tourism industry, the Government of Afghanistan, in addition to providing its basic requirements, such as security and adequate housing facilities, must also work culturally and propagandistically to grow the industry and introduce the tourist attractions to the world. This is possible by holding domestic and international seminars on the history and culture of Afghanistan, encouraging public diplomacy with foreign countries and encouraging foreign citizens to see the historical attractions through invitations (Etelaat newspaper, 28/05/2018)

Research Methodology

This research has been done using descriptive and analytical methodology and through documentary and field studies. Also in this research, the method of collecting documentary information has been used as a reference and taking notes from library documents, and the SWOT strategic technique has been used to analyze the information. The statistical population studied in this article consists of experts and officials of institutions and organizations (Balkh University, Department of Information and Culture and other relevant departments) related to tourism, of which 30 people have been selected as a sample. Then, according to the analysis of the four factors of strength, weakness, threat and opportunities, a questionnaire containing a five-choice question was obtained. In this section, to complete the questionnaires, 30 experts and officials of tourism-related institutions and organizations were obtained. Comment was done. In order to analyze the information and present the strategic model of tourism development, the SWOT analysis method has been used. First, a list of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats was identified by measuring the internal and external environment, and then by asking experts for their opinion. And the officials in charge of ordering and weighing each of these issues and then calculating and analyzing them, the priorities were determined and in order to eliminate or reduce the weaknesses and threats and strengthen and improve the existing strengths and opportunities related to the expansion of tourism in Balkh province, finally appropriate strategies have been presented.

Study Area

Balkh is one of the most important and first-class provinces in northern Afghanistan, the city of Mazar-e-Sharif is the capital of the province, which has great political, economic and population value in northern Afghanistan, Balkh province is located at 29° and 31' north latitude and 68° and 28' east longitude. It shares Afghanistan's border with Tajikistan and Uzbekistan in the north, and inside the country with Kunduz and Samangan in the east, Jawzjan in the west, and Sar-e-Pul and Samangan in the south. The area of the province is 16480 square kilometers according to the Central Statistics Office and 16186 square kilometers according to the information of the Office (UNFPA). In terms of administrative divisions, this province has 14 cities in addition to Mazar-e-Sharif (center) and Hairatan port, which are: Nahrshahi, Dehdadi, Balkh, Dolatabad, Chamtal, Shulgar, Chaharbolak, Keshandeh, Zari, Charkent, Shortepe, Kaldar, Marmol and Kholm. Balkh is one of the provinces of Afghanistan where almost all ethnic groups of Afghanistan such as Uzbeks, Hazaras, Pashtuns and Tajiks live and next to it live Aimaq, Baluch, Arabs and other small ethnic groups (Ansari, 2015, p. 554)

Figure 1: Map of the study area

Tourist attractions of Balkh province

Balkh province today is deeply rooted in history. Balkh was the most famous city of the times, whose thick walls and patient domes still resist the hardships of time, claiming the brilliance of a nucleus of an ancient civilization called Bokhdi. Balkh Bami has been burned and destroyed several times throughout history by the sinister hands and passion of its enemies, but today it is possible to recognize it from the ashes and ruins left. Despite the fact that the city of Balkh has been destroyed several times, today hundreds of items of its relics and monuments are still standing with full force, which attracts millions of tourists from inside and outside the country every year. Old Balkh Today is the place for the emergence of Zoroastrianism, the beginning of farming and putting the yoke on the shoulders of cows, the center of trade between East and West, the birthplace of great intellectuals, a mirror image to reflect the life of the Aryan and Khorasan peoples, It is a nest of Dari language that should not be forgotten with its bright and shiny past.

This city attracts the most tourists in the spring. Because the first of Hamal coincides with the first of Nowruz or the beginning of the national celebration of Nowruz, which is celebrated every year with the presence of hundreds of thousands of guests from inside and outside the country in the city of Mazar-e-Sharif with the flag raising of Hazrat Ali "peace be upon him". After the ceremony, all the guests will go to Balkh province, the birthplace of the national Nowruz celebration. The reality and historical background of this celebration cannot be understood by seeing the city of Mazar-e-Sharif. Because the essence and origin of this celebration is not the city of Mazar-e-Sharif, but this great celebration of the heritage left by the people who lived in the city of Balkh. Therefore, those who come to Mazar-e-Sharif from all over Afghanistan and outside of Afghanistan to celebrate the national celebration of Nowruz in the spring should visit Balkh province to hear the story of this celebration from Nobahar hill, tall towers, destroyed buildings and the green nature of this border. Therefore, Balkh province, with its hundreds of historical monuments with a green surface, attracts millions of people from inside and outside the country every year. And annually adds millions of Afghanis to the treasury of the government and the people of the province. I think it is necessary to introduce some of the historical monuments of this ancient region below (Nazari, 2015, p. 23).

Table 2: List of tourist attractions of Balkh province

No	Name of district	Name of tourist attraction	Location
1	Balkh	Balahesar	Balkh
2	Balkh	City walls	Balkh
3	Balkh	Qale honar dal	Balkh
4	Balkh	Fire temple of Nawbahar	Balkh
5	Balkh	Ayaran tower	Balkh
6	Balkh	Khoja Parsa Masjid	Balkh
7	Dwlatabad	Fire temple of Dehrawan	Dolatabad
8	Nahreshahi	Castle of Takhtapol	Nahreshahi
9	Nahreshahi	Castle of Takhtapol Masjid	Nahreshahi
10	Kholm	Masjid of Charso	Kholm
11	Kholm	Jahan Noma Garden & castle	Kholm
12	Dehdadi	Qale Jangi	Dehdadi
13	Dehdadi	Khanaqa kalan	Dehdadi
14	Mazar e sharif	Shrine of Hazrat e Ali	Mazar e sharif
15	Balkh	Shrine of Abo Hafas	Samarqandian
16	Balkh	Shrine of Ibn khozravia	Balkh
17	Balkh	Shrine of Abo Nasr Balkhi	Balkh
18	Balkh	Chargonbad masjid	Balkh
19	Balkh	Shrine of Rabia Balkhi	Balkh
20	Dawlatabad	Shrine of Abo Horaira	Dolatabad
21	Dehdadi	Chehel Dokhtaran castle	Dehdadi
22	Dehdadi	Chehel soton hill	Dehdadi
23	Chemtal	Jamshid shahr	Chemtal
24	Kholm	shortepa	Nawabad
25	Balkh	Shrine of Molla Mohammad Jan	Balkh
26	Chemtal	Shefa spring	Chemtal
27	Mazar e sharif	Shrine of Mohammad khan shir Ali khan	Mazar e sharif

Research Findings

First stage - presenting the strategies for the development of tourism in Balkh province of Afghanistan, analyzing of environment and identifying internal and external factors.

After studying, identifying the challenges, opportunities and capabilities of tourism in the study area and measuring the indicators that determine the tourism capacity in Balkh province, an appropriate strategy for tourism development was developed. To identify the challenges and opportunities for tourism development in Balkh province, the strategic planning framework and SWOT technique were used to identify strategic issues and formulate appropriate strategies in the following process.

First stage: Determining the goal and prospects of tourism development in Balkh province

Determining the purpose and perspective of the research is: Tourism development in Balkh province in case of increasing social capacities, economic capabilities and ecological-economic development, the ecological capacities of the ecosystem should be maintained and compatible with the environment, resources, natural and historical attractions in Balkh to avoid ecological hazards in the study area. The results show that in Balkh province 16 internal strengths against 14 internal weaknesses and 13 external opportunities against 13 external threats are identified and examined. Thus, a total of 29 strengths and opportunities can be identified as strengths and 27 weaknesses and obstacles as limitations for sustainable tourism development in Balkh province. The results are presented in Table (3).

Table 3: Shows strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

Dimensions	Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
Ecological	S1- Existence of pristine ecological natural landscapes S2- Diversity and environmental richness including rivers, waterfalls, hot springs, mountains and ... S3- Existence of multiple ecosystems (protected - no hunting) S4- Convenient geographical location and easy access to the area, located on the tourist route and close to tourist attractions in the center of the province, S5- Strategic position of the region in the country (existence of Hairatan commercial port), S6- Adjacent to Jawzjan, Sar-e-Pul, Faryab and Samangan transit roads and being located between the above provinces	W1- The declining trend of some elements of natural landscapes W2- Inaccessibility of some natural attractions W3- Sensitivity and fragility of ecosystems

Sociocultural	S7- Existence of important historical-memorial monuments and cultural structures, S8- Diversity of ethnicities, customs and traditions and valuable cultural manifestations (celebration of Nawroz), S 9- Diversity of rural and nomadic life patterns (nomads), S10- The culture of hospitality in the region, especially among villagers and nomads, S11- Existence of a sense of cooperation and participation among the people of the region, S12- Paying attention to the protection and restoration of historical monuments in the study area	W4- Inadequacy and lack of health and service facilities, accommodation and welfare in the study area, W5- Lack of recreational facilities for tourism, W6- Lack of proper advertising and information in the field of tourist attractions in the country, W7- Lack of tourism culture among local communities, W8- Low familiarity and lack of training of local residents to participate in tourism activities, W9- Low level of literacy and lack of awareness about the benefits of tourism in the region, W10- Lack of specialized and trained personnel in the field of tourism in these areas.
Economic	S13- Existence of domestic tourism model in the province (family - visiting relatives), S14- Existence of tourism and welfare services including hospitals, hotels, recreation centers, etc.	W11- Economic poverty and deprivation in the region, W12- Low quality access and transportation network.
Political Security	S15- The belief of the officials in the development of tourism as one of the appropriate mechanisms for the development and job creation of the region, S16- Existence of security in the study area.	W13- Insecurity of communication network, W14- Low management capacity in the province in the field of tourism in the region.
Dimensions	Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
Ecological	O1- Provincial border position and opportunity to attract tourists from neighboring country (Uzbekistan),	T1- Destruction of vegetation and agricultural lands, T2- The spread of environmental pollution, T3- Multiple tourist attractions in neighboring areas of Balkh province.
Sociocultural	O2- Balkh reputation as the mother of cities (Umm al-Balad) in Afghanistan, O3- Carrying out researches and historical and cultural studies regarding the study area, O4- Existence of media and social networks in tourism development in the country, O5- Existence of specialized tourism forces and planners in the country.	T4- Changes in traditional and local culture in the study area due to tourism T5- The traditional nature of the people of the region and the possibility of cultural confrontation between residents and tourists T6- Lack of appropriate facilities and infrastructure in the study area to attract and retain tourists

Economic	<p>O6- Paying attention to the reconstruction or presentation of new infrastructures in the study area, such as (transportation, communication roads, hotels and restaurants, etc.),</p> <p>O7- Support of some foreign institutions for the development of tourism in the country,</p> <p>O8- World Bank support for tourism development in the region under the name of National Solidarity Project in sectors (roads, health and education centers,</p> <p>O9- The growing trend of domestic tourism markets,</p> <p>O10- Possibility of attracting foreign investors and Afghans living abroad.</p>	<p>T7- Limited marketing and advertising activities in the tourism sector of the country,</p> <p>T8- Lack of credit-financial facilities in the field of tourism to organize attractions,</p> <p>T9- Reluctance of the private sector and investors to invest in tourism due to insecurity,</p> <p>T10- Increasing the price of land and stock exchanges and, of course, increasing the financial burden to create tourism equipment and facilities.</p>
Political- Security	<p>O11- Attention of the Environment Organization to environmental protection in the country,</p> <p>O13- Emphasis of related ministries such as environment and rural development on the development of sustainable tourism in the country,</p> <p>O14- Increasing government attention to planning and investment in the tourism sector.</p>	<p>T11- Lack of integrated management in the field of tourism,</p> <p>T12- Inadequate policy for tourism management,</p> <p>T13- Weakness of space management and planning regulations (national, regional, urban, etc.) in Afghanistan.</p>

Step 2: Formation of SWOT matrix (identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the region)

Formation of internal factors evaluation matrices (IFE) and external factors evaluation (EFE) according to the presented opinions and calculations and on these opinions in order to evaluate the four factors, the table of internal factors evaluation matrix and factor matrix was formed. It was externalized which indicates the score of importance, coefficient of importance and rank and final score of each of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats from the perspective of the respondent group.

Internal and external factor evaluation matrix

By identifying the key and influential factors of the internal and external environment, it is time to evaluate the factors. In other words, an evaluation matrix of internal and external factors must be formed.

To complete the evaluation matrix of internal and external factors, the steps are as follows.

Determining the importance or average of factors: The above factors were weighed through a questionnaire technique designed by a sample size of 30 experts and officials to achieve accurate results by quantifying the factors.

Determining the relative weight of each factor: Based on the sum of the average relative weight of each factor was obtained (the mean of each factor was divided by the sum of the mean).

Determining the rank strings of each factor to determine the rank of 1 to 4, the average domain method is used, which is shown in Table (4).

Table 4: show the rank of strings of each factor.

Rank	Average range	Internal Factors	External Factors
4	5-4	strength	Opportunity
3	4-3	strength	Opportunity
2	4-3	weakness	Treat
1	5-4	weakness	Treat

Calculating the final score of the factors: Then the relative weight of each factor was multiplied by the ranks of each factor and the final score of the factors was obtained.

Table No. 5: Internal Factor Evaluation Matrix

Dimensions	Strengths	Average	Relative weight	Rank	Score
Ecological	S 1- Existence of pristine ecological natural landscapes	4/03	0/038	3	0/115
	S2- Diversity and environmental richness including rivers, waterfalls, hot springs, mountains and ...	4	0/038	3	0/114
	S3- Existence of multiple ecosystems (protected - no hunting)	2/7	0/026	3	0/077
	S4- Convenient geographical location and easy access to the region, location on the tourist route and proximity of tourist attractions to the provincial capital	3/93	0/037	3	0/112
	S5- Strategic position of the region in the country (existence of Hairatan commercial port)	3/93	0/037	3	0/112
	S6- Adjacent to the transit road of Jawzjan, Sar-e-Pul, Faryab and Samangan and being located between the above provinces	3/97	0/038	3	0/113
Sociocultural	S7- Existence of important historical-memorial monuments and cultural structures	4/33	0/041	4	0/165
	S8- Diversity of ethnicities, customs and traditions and valuable cultural manifestations (Nowruz celebration)	4/07	0/039	3	0/116
	S 9- Diversity of rural and nomadic life patterns (nomads)	2/97	0/028	3	0/085
	S10- Culture and hospitality in the region, especially among its villagers and nomads	3/53	0/034	3	0/101
	S11- Existence of a sense of cooperation and participation among the people of the region.	3/17	0/030	3	0/091
	S12- Paying attention to the protection and restoration of historical monuments in the study area	3/37	0/032	3	0/096
Economic	S13- Existence of domestic tourism model in the province (family - visiting relatives)	3/33	0/032	3	0/095
	S14- Existence of tourism and welfare services including hospitals, hotels, recreation centers, etc.	3/07	0/029	3	0/088

Political-security	S15- The belief of the officials in the development of tourism as one of the appropriate mechanisms for the development and job creation of the region.	3/13	0/029	3	0/088
	S16- Existence of security in the study area	3/43	0/030	3	0/089
Dimensions	Weaknesses				
Ecological	W1- The declining trend of some elements of natural landscapes	3/53	0/034	2	0/067
	W2- Inaccessibility of some natural attractions	2/83	0/027	2	0/054
	W3- Sensitivity and fragility of ecosystems	3/13	0/030	2	0/060
Sociocultural	W4- Inadequacy and lack of health and service facilities, accommodation and welfare in the study area	3/37	0/032	2	0/064
	W5- Lack of recreational facilities for tourism	3/43	0/033	2	0/065
	W6- Lack of proper advertising and information in the field of tourist attractions in the country	3/33	0/032	2	0/063
	W7- Lack of tourism culture among local communities	3/43	0/033	2	0/065
	W8- Low familiarity and lack of training of local residents to participate in tourism activities.	3/43	0/033	2	0/065
	W9- Low level of literacy and lack of awareness about the benefits of tourism in the region	3/5	0/033	2	0/067
	W10- Lack of specialized and trained personnel in the field of tourism in these areas.	3/63	0/035	2	0/069
Economic	W11- Economic poverty and deprivation in the region	3/63	0/035	2	0/069
	W12- Low quality access and transportation network	3/53	0/034	1	0/034
Political-security	W13 - Insecurity of communication network	3/6	0/034	1	0/034
	W14- Low management capacity in the province in the field of tourism in the region	3/63	0/035	1	0/035
	Total internal factors (strengths and weaknesses)	104/96	1/000		2/481

Table No. 6: External Factor Evaluation Matrix

Dimensions	Opportunity (O)	Average	Relative weight	Rank	Score
Ecological	O1- The border position of the province and the opportunity to attract tourists from the neighboring country of Uzbekistan	3/83	0/044	3	0/132
Sociocultural	O2- Balkh is famous as the mother of cities (Umm al-Balad) in Afghanistan	4/33	0/050	4	0/199
	O3- Conducting researches, historical and cultural studies regarding the study area	3/57	0/041	3	0/123
	O4- Existence of media and social networks in tourism development in Afghanistan	3/43	0/039	3	0/118
	O5- Existence of specialized tourism and planning forces in Afghanistan	3	0/034	3	0/103

Economic	O6- Paying attention to the reconstruction or presentation of new infrastructures in the study area, such as (transportation, communication roads and restaurants, etc.).	3/17	0/036	3	0/109
	O7- Support of some foreign institutions for the development of tourism in Afghanistan	3/43	0/039	3	0/118
	O8- World Bank support for tourism development in the region under the name of National Solidarity Project in sectors (roads, health and education centers)	3/23	0/037	3	0/111
	O9- The growing trend of domestic tourism markets	3/5	0/040	3	0/120
	O10- Possibility of attracting foreign investors and Afghans living abroad	3/37	0/039	3	0/116
Political-security	O11- Attention of the Environment Organization to environmental protection in the country	3/3	0/038	3	0/114
	O14- Increasing government attention to planning and investment in the tourism sector.	3/03	0/035	3	0/104
	O13- Emphasis of related ministries such as environment and rural development on the development of sustainable tourism in the country	3/13	0/036	3	0/108
Dimensions	Threats (T)				
Ecological	T1- Destruction of vegetation and agricultural lands	3/47	0/040	2	0/080
	T2- The spread of environmental pollution	2/97	0/034	2	0/068
	T3- Multiple tourist attractions in neighboring areas of Balkh province	2/77	0/032	2	0/064
Social	T4- Changes in traditional and local culture in the study area due to tourism	2/73	0/031	2	0/063
	T5- The traditional nature of the people of the region and the possibility of cultural confrontation between residents and tourists	2/8	0/032	2	0/064
	T6- Lack of appropriate facilities and infrastructure in the study area to attract and retain tourists	3/4	0/039	2	0/078
Economic	T7- Limited marketing and advertising activities in the tourism sector of the country	3/17	0/036	2	0/073
	T8- Lack of credit-financial facilities in the field of tourism to organize attractions	3/6	0/041	2	0/083
	T9- Reluctance of private sector and investors to invest in tourism due to insecurity	3/57	0/041	2	0/082
	T10- Increasing the price of land and stock exchanges and increasing the financial burden to create tourism equipment and facilities	3/23	0/037	2	0/074
Political	T11- Lack of integrated management in the field of tourism	3/53	0/040	2	0/081
	T12- Inadequate policy for tourism management	3/83	0/044	1	0/044
	T13- Weakness of space management and planning regulations (national, regional, urban, etc.) in Afghanistan	3/8	0/044	1	0/044
Total external factors (opportunities and threats)		87/19	1/000	64	2/470

Based on the internal and external factors evaluation matrix, the average of all internal and external factors was above average (based on the Likert scale of the questionnaire), so all factors were considered to provide a strategy. But based on the final score, which was multiplied by the relative weight of each factor, in total, the internal factors of the component of the existence of tourist attractions (diversity of ethnicities, customs and traditions and valuable cultural manifestations (Nowruz celebration) with a final weight of 0.039 The most important strengths and components (lack of specialized and trained personnel in the field of tourism in these areas) with a final weight of 0.035 are the most important weaknesses. In the set of external factors of opportunity (Balkh's reputation as the mother of cities (Umm al-Balad) in Afghanistan) with a final weight of 0.050 and against the threat (weakness of rules and regulations of space management and planning (national, regional, urban and ...) in Afghanistan) with a final weight of 0.044 are in the top priority.

Step 3 – Adapt, compare and present the strategy

The SWOT adaptive matrix consists of a two-dimensional coordinate table, each of which represents a strategy set. According to the identified internal and external factors, an adaptive SWOT matrix was used, which indicates possible strategies by pairwise comparison of each of the internal and external factors with each other table of No.7.

Table No.7: possible strategies by pairwise comparison of each of the internal and external factors.

Aggressive Strategies (strengths and opportunities)	Review Strategies (Weaknesses and opportunities)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Using the security in the study area to attract the attention of Afghan institutions and investors living abroad to develop tourism and create jobs in the region. 2- Utilizing pristine and ecological natural attractions to develop and attract tourists to create job opportunities and increase income for local people. 3- Using the strategic position of the region, proximity to neighboring countries and provinces for tourism and inter-provincial tourism development. 4- Strengthening the sense of cooperation and participation of local people and providing the ground for the reconstruction of attractions, services and infrastructure (hotels, hospitals and recreation centers) better for tourists. 5- Empowering local government and popular institutions for tourism development in the study area. 6- Strengthening the culture of hospitality and participation among the villagers in order to institutionalize regulations and protect ecosystems and natural landscapes. 7- Strengthening the social capabilities of local people, including trust and social cohesion and interactions, local expert forces, social acceptance of villagers regarding tourism and the culture of tourism of villagers to promote the tourism program. 8- Strengthening the local management system for the protection of historical and cultural monuments. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review and strengthen appropriate facilities and infrastructure in the study area using Afghan investors living abroad. 2. Review marketing and advertising activities and using media and social networks to develop tourism. 3. Review and prevent the destruction of natural landscapes and ecosystems using the attention of the Environmental Organization to protect the process of destruction. 4. Reviewing the training and professionalization of the responsible tourism forces by using experts and planners at the national level. 5. Review and empower local residents and train them using tourism planners and their participation in tourism activities. 6. Review the economic situation of the region and transportation access networks using the support of the World Bank to develop tourism in the sectors of road construction, health centers, education and job creation. 7. Proper organization and use of the border position of the province to attract tourists. 8. Review to inform, educate and institutionalize the culture of tourism by using the support of foreign institutions and the support of the World Bank in the tourism sector. 9. Review of policies and optimal management in the province in the field of tourism.

<p>9- Using media, social networks and local experts to develop tourism and attracting the attention of officials to plan for tourism in the study area.</p> <p>10- Preserving and using traditional values and holding Nawroz celebrations (Rose Festival) and attracting the attention of tourists in the region.</p>	
<p>Competitive Strategies (ST)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Develop a comprehensive plan for the development of tourism in the region to preserve vegetation and agricultural lands using natural and pristine ecological landscapes without the slightest destructive effects. * Creating a culture to comply with the rules and educating tourists to reduce biological pollution with the support of tourism officials and planners. * Diversification in integrated management in the field of tourism in the country by using the relevant institutions and tourism organizations. * Diversify the rules and regulations of space management and planning at different levels with the support of the authorities. * Diversify the infrastructure of investors to invest in tourism using the strategic position of the region. * Diversification of the cultural and educational program to the sensitivity of change and the possibility of cultural confrontation between residents using the sense of cooperation and popular participation, customs and traditions and valuable cultural manifestations such as the celebration of Nowruz in the region. * Diversify the development of credit-financial facilities in the field of tourism using tourism and welfare services, including hospitals, hotels, leisure centers, etc. * Diversification and development of planning, marketing and advertising activities in the tourism sector by using the attractions and introducing historical monuments and the privilege of proximity to neighbors. * Laying ground for private investors using the security of study area. 	<p>Defensive Strategies (WT)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Plan to prevent the destruction of natural landscapes and agricultural lands. * Appropriate and consistent planning to reduce environmental pollution and prevent the fragility of ecosystems. * Develop educational programs among local communities to raise awareness and culture of tourism in the region. * Development of advertising and information programs to introduce tourist attractions. * Develop rules and regulations to improve integrated management and select experts for appropriate policy management for tourism. * Development and construction of service, welfare and health infrastructure for accommodation and reception of tourists in the region. * Planning to reduce insecurity and pave the way for private investors to invest in tourism development and elimination of economic poverty and deprivation in the region. * Develop comprehensive programs to raise the level of awareness and literacy of local residents and local authorities to strengthen participation in tourism activities and protection of attractions.

Position evaluation matrix and strategy action

At this stage, using strategic factors affecting the identification of challenges and opportunities for tourism development in Balkh, strategies were developed and the point position of priority strategies for tourism development was determined. Position assessment and strategic action: According to the evaluation matrix of internal and external factors and scores obtained from the sum of internal and external factors, the strategic position of the study area is identified in the SWOT analysis chart to identify challenges and opportunities for tourism development. Based on the final score of the internal factors evaluation matrix (IFE = 2.481) and the

external factors evaluation matrix (EFE = 2.470), the strategic position of the study area in the SWOT analysis chart is in the fourth quarter, so the "defensive strategy" is preferred in the region of study area. (Figure 2).

(Figure 2): Evaluation matrix shape of location of the study area.

Conclusion

In recent years, tourism as a harmless industry has become a rich source of income in world trade and an important element in improving and regulating the trade balance and balance of payments of many countries. Meanwhile, Balkh province is one of the cultural and historical provinces of Afghanistan, one of the oldest and origins of urbanization and civilization, whose rich and extensive historical and cultural heritage has a high potential for cultural richness and tourism development. Based on the analysis of research findings and studies, it is inferred that this province has a good potential for tourism development. But in order to reach the tourism hub at the national, regional and global levels, it needs strategic-structural and functional planning in infrastructure and other tourism sectors, as well as urban spaces. Considering the situation of strengths and opportunities for tourism development in the study area and on the other hand, the weaknesses of the threats that exist in the process of tourism development in the province, effective approaches to this process according to the SWOT model indicate that the weakness and lack of specialized and trained personnel in the field of tourism is one of the main causes of underdeveloped tourism in Balkh province and the region. Based on the studies conducted, it can be stated that the study area, despite having high tourism potentials, is currently lacking in tourism. The main reason for this is the weakness of tourism planning and management. What is obvious is that the transformation of this region into a tourist hub at the national and regional levels requires the use of integrated management based on environmental, social, security and economic elements. In the end, it should be noted that in addition to the need for weaknesses, strengths, threats and opportunities ahead, the tourism industry is essential in any region. In order to achieve sustainable tourism and develop sustainable tourism, especially in Balkh province, it is necessary to use the experiences gained in different parts of the world, along with changes in travel patterns and interests of tourists in the world.

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